

TACKLING HOSTILITY TOWARDS SCIENTISTS

Supplementary Material

A photograph of a white lighthouse with a black lantern room, situated on a rocky island. The lighthouse is the central focus, with waves crashing against the shore in the foreground. The sky is a clear, pale blue. The text 'GUIDELINES' is centered in the upper half of the image, and 'FORTIFY RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS' is centered in the lower half, both within a white rectangular frame.

GUIDELINES

**FORTIFY RESEARCH
INSTITUTIONS**

Department	Responsible person's name	Role in the crisis team	Availability	Availability after working hours
Management Level				
Communications Department, Social Media Team, Community Management				
Technical Department, IT, Security				
Legal Department				
Colleagues				
External cooperation partners				
Crisis contact overview			Template	

A photograph of a surfer in a black wetsuit riding a large, curling wave. The water is a deep teal color, and the wave's crest is breaking into white foam. A white-bordered rectangular box is superimposed over the center of the image, containing text. The overall scene is dynamic and captures the power of the ocean.

TOOLKIT

**PRACTICING
SUPPORT STRATEGIES**

THE SIX TYPES OF THINKING HATS

The Six Thinking Hats is a role-playing model developed by Edward de Bono in 1986. Each hat represents a different lens or perspective on a particular issue and is an insightful activity that prevents narrow thinking. It serves as a team-based problem solving and brainstorming technique that can be used to explore problems through various perspectives in order to uncover options that might otherwise be overlooked.

White Hat: Facts

Objective data analysis.

Analytical thinking with an emphasis on facts and feasibility.

Black Hat: Caution

Critical judgment for identifying risks and flaws.

Critical, skeptical, focused on risks and identifying problems.

Blue Hat: Process

Facilitation and process control.

Structured thinking, high-level overview of the situation, the big picture.

Red Hat: Feelings

Emotional and intuitive responses.

Emotional thinking, subjective feelings, perception and opinion.

Yellow Hat: Benefits

Positive thinking for exploring benefits.

Thinking optimistic, speculative, develop best-case scenarios.

Green Hat: Creativity

Creative and innovative ideas.

Associative thinking, new ideas, brainstorming, out-of-the-box.

The following case studies can be used for the exercise **A2 Changing perspective** . They are fictional but inspired by real incidents and by a recent survey on the frequency, prevalence and types of hostility experienced by researchers in Germany.

Please note: The case studies include descriptions or language that could be considered offensive or triggering. They are intended for educational purposes only.

A2 Changing perspective

Incident cards exercise

Instructions

Lena Hoffmann, a PhD-candidate in Biomedical Research, recently published a study on nutritional supplements in a well-regarded journal. After sharing her findings in a LinkedIn post, she began receiving dismissive comments questioning her methods and suggesting she was “overconfident” for her career stage. As the discussion spread beyond professional circles, users tagged her directly and implied she was “too junior to speak publicly” on health issues, asking whether she “really understands the basics of clinical research”.

When Lena mentioned the volume of hostile messages to her supervisor, he dismissed it as “part of being visible”. Meanwhile, comments continued to circulate, with some warning that “people will remember your name” if her conclusions prove wrong. Lena continues to respond professionally but feels increasingly isolated and uncertain about further public engagement.

An opinion piece on antisemitism in post-war Germany by Prof. Erik Vogel, a 68-year-old historian, initially prompted angry emails disputing his credibility. Weeks later, a far-right blog labelled him a “biased historian serving foreign interests” and shared details of his upcoming public lectures, encouraging readers to confront him. The post spread widely, and Erik began receiving messages calling him a “liar,” a “traitor” and using antisemitic slurs.

Recently, he found antisemitic stickers placed repeatedly on his car while parked on campus. Although no explicit threats were made, several emails warned that “traitors eventually face consequences”. Erik has reported the incidents but continues teaching while closely monitoring the situation.

Dr. Carlos Rivera's vaccine research initially received dismissive online remarks questioning his independence. After a radio interview, coordinated comment campaigns appeared under his publications, accusing him of deliberately misleading the public. Soon after, links to his institutional profile circulated in activist forums, resulting in a steady stream of near-identical emails demanding retractions.

Some messages questioned whether he was "really qualified to speak for the German public", referencing his name and background. While most emails avoided direct threats, several warned that scientists who "lie" should not feel safe behind universities. Carlos continues his work but is increasingly reluctant to communicate outside academic channels.

Dr. Nina Kowalski's article on gender bias in AI first prompted sarcastic responses questioning her expertise. Following a podcast appearance, forum discussions began focusing on her background rather than her arguments. Commenters described her as "too emotional", "an activist" or "personally invested" to be scientifically objective and suggested she was invited to "add a female perspective" rather than for her research competence.

More recently, screenshots of her online profiles have been shared in hostile threads, inviting others to "challenge" her directly.

A meme was circulated called "Angry Nina", often accompanied by remarks about her appearance, tone or temperament rather than her work. She has also noticed that the same few self-proclaimed journalists frequently appear at her talks and seminars, asking intrusive questions about her schedule, travel plans or whether she attends events alone. While none of the interactions are overtly threatening, the sustained, gendered attention has made her feel monitored. Nina is unsure whether maintaining a public academic presence is worth the ongoing exposure.

Environmental engineer Dr. Priya Kapoor presented a waste management proposal at an open city hall debate. This was part of a contested plan to modernise a nearby waste processing site affecting local residents and businesses. During the meeting, a local councilman dismissed her ideas as “spicy”, adding that the issue required “less emotion and more hard engineering”, prompting laughter from parts of the audience. After a newspaper interview, critical blog posts circulated on social media, tagging Priya directly and questioning her qualifications.

Comment sections grew increasingly sceptical, suggesting she did not understand “how these systems actually work” and framing her proposals as out of touch with local economic and neighbourhood concerns, with some accusing her of “experimenting on our district.” Her inbox soon filled with messages urging her to “leave this to real engineers”, questioning whether she was the right person to speak publicly. While remaining the project lead, Priya has reduced her public visibility and now delegates media appearances to senior male colleagues.

The following fictional scenario can be used for the exercise *A3 Rewriting the narrative*. This scenario describes a public engagement event with a presentation by early career researchers and includes different points of tension and possibilities for interaction.

The scenario will take the facilitator approx. 5–7 minutes to read aloud. Participants will listen to the scenario from the perspective of fictional personas, for which character sheets are available on the following slides.

It is a hot summer evening at the city's Museum of Natural History. For one night only, the building is open until midnight for the Long Night of Science. The air is humid, and the ventilation system struggles to keep up. Volunteers fan themselves at the info desk. Many rooms feel stuffy, but the air buzzes with conversation and anticipation. The event was organised by the museum's marketing and events team, who were eager to attract a more "urban, educated adult crowd" – a departure from the usual daytime family focus. They marketed the programme using the slogan: "*Science Fights Fake News: Real Research Not Rants*".

The Berlin-wide festival has over 1500 individual events in the 2025 programme and is intended to show science that is otherwise "hidden" from the public in order to "promote real research, taking a stance against fake news, misinterpretation and conspiracy theories". Tickets cost 5€ city-wide, but some visitors didn't realise that certain spaces have limited capacity or are hard to access via lift and that navigating the wider programme and travelling between venues can be difficult.

The corridors are filled with a mix of visitors of all ages – families with children, students, older guests with museum maps in hand and people chatting at the pop-up bar areas over a glass of wine or soda. The lighting is slightly dimmed and a few exhibits have been temporarily moved to make space for live presentations.

Some people are wandering between rooms; others are already waiting in front of the event spaces, scanning the programme booklets, as the rooms are quite busy, with only a few seats available.

At the corner of the second floor, a group of 3 early career researchers are preparing to present their project as part of the *Long Night of Sciences*. The group has prepared a lively visual presentation but noticed that despite the microphone, unfortunately the acoustics of the room are not great, especially with lots of visitors circulating around the open gallery. The walls show images of city parks, alleyways, rooftops and various animals that live in these environments. Beside the presentation space and microphone, there is a display table with objects and flyers and a large TV-screen showing a title slide: "Birds in the Noise: Studying Urban Soundscapes and Wildlife".

As the audience slowly gathers, one of the researchers, standing by the laptop, gives a brief nod and begins the presentation with a provocative statement with a sense of urgency: "We all know cities are loud – but few people realise that for birds, this can be more than an annoyance. In fact, in some cases, it's life-threatening." They then explain that their team studies how urban noise pollution influences the behaviour and wellbeing of common city birds, raising questions about human responsibility towards the natural world. ...

... The presentation begins with a clear but technical description of their main research question: how do different levels and types of noise affect the feeding, nesting and communication behaviours of birds in urban settings? The researcher notes their data collection methods – microphones and motion-sensitive cameras placed in city parks, trees and near construction sites – but the terminology and detail feel overwhelming to some.

They play two short audio clips. The first, recorded in a quiet park at dawn, reveals crisp bird calls. The second, from a noisy roadside near a tram line, is chaotic and hard to distinguish. The presenter explains changes in call volume, frequency and timing can influence territorial defence and mating. They add: “This isn’t just about noise being annoying. It’s about cities becoming biologically uninhabitable to species that were once part of our everyday environment. And yet, most people don’t notice.”

Next, the researchers describe observations of nesting behaviour across sites with varying noise levels – noting increased nest abandonment or more concealed nests in louder areas. They mention camera traps and daily visits in urban parks, roadsides and residential zones.

When the presenter briefly references capturing and fitting some birds with small sound sensors, their tone becomes noticeably defensive.

They say these tagging procedures followed animal welfare guidelines but offer no visuals or detailed explanations, leaving some audience members uneasy and ethically conflicted. There is a murmur in the crowd about animal rights and the speaker seems caught off guard. They address the point, noting that of course the museum studies animals, including their behaviour and that can mean running live experiments, but the regulations are very strict; the same that apply to medical drug testing or cosmetics. This study is minimally invasive, even though it might sound intrusive or alarming to non-experts.

Towards the end of the presentation, the speaker shares a few images of the research sites: fenced-off tree lines, roof gardens, tram stops. One researcher reflects on the project’s broader implications, suggesting the findings urge us to reconsider urban space as a shared environment between humans and non-human residents. They emphasise that sound is a lens to notice this. They suggest that city planning rarely considers wildlife or when it does, the measures like bat boxes, bird houses or insect hotels can be tokenistic and more for human benefit. They invite the audience to imagine what it would mean to listen more carefully and end with a call to help make urban spaces more liveable for all species.

They thank the audience and invite questions or comments. There is a short pause for questions. The room is quiet at first, followed by polite applause.

Marco Klein

Age 41

Occupation Logistics Manager

Education Vocational training

Income €2,800/month

Values: Practicality, family, safety, respect

Motivation for attending:

Entertaining his two children (ages 8 and 10)

Behaviour:

Follows conventional media, avoids politics, trusts experts but dislikes jargon, may disengage if he feels out of depth or that his kids are bored or excluded.

Expectation 1: Presentation should be accessible for kids, without needing to ask for clarification.

Expectation 2: Wants to see if academic work is a good use of public funds, especially when his own work-life balance is tight.

Dr. Lena Vogt

Age 34

Occupation Postdoc in Sociology

Education PhD

Income €3,200/month

Values: Academic integrity, social impact, interdisciplinarity

Motivation for attending:

Supportive curiosity, mild professional rivalry

Behaviour:

Reads *Die Zeit*, uses *Twitter/X* for academic news, often questions methods in cross-discipline presentations, slow to trust quantitative claims, compares everything to her own fieldwork.

Expectation 1: Science presentations should be nuanced and include urban socio-economic factors affecting animal environments.

Expectation 2: Science presentations should not oversimplify the underlying research.

Hilde Baumann

Age

72

Occupation Retired Nurse

Education Secondary school

Income

€1,600/month (pension)

Values: Kindness, care, tradition, accessibility

Motivation for attending:

Bonding outing with her 6-year-old grandson

Behaviour:

Watches public TV (*ARD*), dislikes loud environments, values simple explanations, reluctant to ask questions but attentive and grateful when included.

Expectation 1: Anticipates that there might be difficult to understand technical terms, and dreads feeling "stupid" in front of her grandchild.

Expectation 2: Hopes for more hands-on interaction; feels side-lined if the experience is too visual/audio-based without accessibility consideration.

Tanja Korkmaz

Age

37

Occupation

Independent science
blogger

Education

BA in Communication

Income

€1,200 -1,800/month

Values: Transparency, accountability, public engagement

Motivation for attending:

Looking for content and critique

Behaviour:

Reads blogs, non-mainstream media, posts sharp *Twitter/X* threads, looks for contradictions or media-friendly moments, dislikes inaccessible science but values genuine outreach.

Expectation 1: Ethics or funding should be explicitly addressed during science presentations.

Expectation 2: Researchers should have received some media-training and should not avoid critical questions.

Nadja Becker

Age

48

Occupation High school art teacher

Education Teaching degree

Income

€3,100/month

Values: Creativity, critical thinking, empathy, independence

Motivation for attending:

Inspiration for cross-disciplinary lessons

Behaviour:

Listens to podcasts, reads *Der Spiegel*, doesn't question science per se but resents elitism, avoids confrontation, looks for emotion or relevance over data.

Expectation 1: Curious about emotional and visual storytelling (not just raw data points).

Expectation 2: Interested to see how her subject area is valued in this space.

Emre Reimers

Age 21

Occupation Undergrad student
(Psychology & Media Studies)

Education Bachelor's ongoing

Income €850/month

Values: Novelty, curiosity, social connection

Motivation for attending:

Spontaneous choice for a fun evening

Behaviour:

Watches *YouTube* science channels, open but easily distracted, laughs during awkward moments, unsure if they “belong” but eager to engage if it feels relaxed or interactive.

Expectation 1: Often feels like an outsider among academics –unsure when or how they’re allowed to engage.

Expectation 2: Looks forward to an interactive, engaging presentation, that doesn't feel “too dry” or scripted.

Jörg Albrecht

Age

55

Occupation Civil Engineer

Education Master's degree

Income

€3,700/month
(pension+public speeches)

Values: Nature, patience, accuracy, community

Motivation for attending:

Passion for birds

Behaviour:

Subscribes to birding newsletters, active in local birdwatching group, skeptical of any animal research, may ask detailed questions, dislikes when animals are treated as data.

Expectation 1: Intelligent animals such as birds should be treated respectfully by researchers at all times.

Expectation 2: Bird's own adaptive agency should be recognised.

A Researcher Support Team addresses incidents of harassment and intimidation against researchers. The roles, responsibilities and capabilities of the team must be clearly defined and visible to researchers; otherwise, support might be underutilised.

The worksheet provides an overview of how the various departments and roles within a research institution could offer support. No institution has everything, but by identifying what you have and what you need, you can start to build your response team and develop a shared understanding of what is still required.

These worksheet are adapted from the Researcher Support Consortium's [Toolkit for Institutions](#)

Departments that may be able to provide support to researchers under attack, along with their suggested roles.

Select the support options that apply to your organisation.

Academic Affairs and Staff Assistance:

- Provide trainings and materials on how to manage harassment and intimidation
- Write and distribute policies on harassment and intimidation
- Serve as/provide an advocate for a harassed individual within the university
- Help with conflict management among faculty or between faculty and students
- Provide consultation services for the mental health and well-being of the targeted person and other affected faculty
- Refer affected person to community and national organisations that can help them protect their mental health

Human Resources

- Help the affected person document intimidation and harassment
- Help the person plan a strategy for how to respond to harassment
- Provide support in discussing intimidation and harassment with the person's department chair and/or dean
- Assist in facilitating connections between colleagues who have had similar experiences
- Investigate harassment and intimidation complaints by conducting relevant interviews and reviewing evidence

Departments that may be able to provide support to researchers under attack, along with their suggested roles.

Select the support options that apply to your organisation.

Senior Leadership

- Provide messaging surrounding the importance of academic freedom to the university's mission and the university's commitment to supporting targeted individuals
- Anticipate risks for more vulnerable researchers while also showing an interest in their work
- If desired by the harassed person, help them prepare a brief message or holding statement of support about their situation for circulation within the university
- Meet with the person being harassed and assure them they have wider university support
- Provide education and information on intimidation and harassment, including information on current trends and resources for mitigating the risk of abuse and responding to abuse

Senior Leadership (ongoing)

- Help the harassed person file a harassment report
- Identify alternative classroom and office spaces if necessary
- Create contingency plans in case the abuse persists long enough to affect researchers' professional obligations, such as teaching
- Connect the person to other departments (e.g., IT, Human Resources) and offer to coordinate efforts with other offices as needed
- Proactively help faculty at a high risk of experiencing harassment anticipate risks while also showing an interest in their work

Departments that may be able to provide support to researchers under attack, along with their suggested roles.

Select the support options that apply to your organisation.

Security

- Assess the threat level
- Assess the potential for a criminal investigation
- Serve as a liaison between the harassed person and local police
- Provide escort services as needed

Information Technology

- Help change and monitor university email accounts and phone systems
- Remove personal information from university websites, social media and public-facing directories
- Help to protect and make private any related course material and syllabi
- Help the person change their social media privacy settings and passwords
- Provide consultation on digital security
- Assign a point person to monitor harassing messages for escalating threats and for evidence that could be used in a criminal investigation
- Assist in reporting harassment and intimidation to relevant platforms
- Help the individual document the harassment

Departments that may be able to provide support to researchers under attack, along with their suggested roles.

Select the support options that apply to your organisation.

Public Relations / Comms Lead

- Develop communication strategies for responding to harassment and intimidation
- Help with public messaging, media inquiries and social media
- Release public statements in support of the harassed individual
- Prepare staff to respond to harassing phone calls and other inquiries by providing them with pre-crafted scripts to use on phone calls
- Help the harassed person develop a personal communication strategy for how to respond to harassment
- Serve as a liaison between the person and any interested media

Office of Diversity, Inclusion and Equity

- Address harassment or abuse related to a person's racial, ethnic, gender or LGBTQIA+ status
- Provide support to others who share a demographic identity similar to that of the targeted individual
- Provide trainings and materials on how to manage harassment and intimidation

The following argumentation aid helps to build arguments for bringing about change in an institution. These arguments should convince different groups in an institution to make researcher support against hostility a strategic priority.

Depending on the institution's specific priorities and on the target groups, the argumentation may change. Use the aid as inspiration and starting point.

INSTITUTIONAL PRIORITY	NEGATIVE IMPACT OF HOSTILITY TOWARDS RESEARCHERS	
Reputation and Research Excellence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Disrupts researcher productivity ● Affects institutional reputation for research excellence 	
Academic Freedom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher silencing, compromising academic freedom and research ethics 	
Equity, Diversity and Inclusion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Disproportionate targeting of minority groups/ marginalised researchers 	
Collegiality, Positive Research Culture, Transparency, Integrity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Causes researcher isolation and undermines credibility ● Mental health crisis ● Could emerge positively from the situation: Clear communication structures and support mechanisms addresses internal silos and builds trust 	
Remuneration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Financial costs of attacks on researchers 	
C1 Building a case for action	Argumentation aid	Cheat sheet

The following Impact x Effort compass provides participants with a framework for deciding which changes should be made immediately and which are less urgent or require more support to implement.

You can use the compass on paper or transfer it to a larger surface with tape or chalk.

maybe

HIGH EFFORT

next

LOW IMPACT

HIGH IMPACT

later

LOW EFFORT

now

The following cases and exercises have been developed by Felix Krohn. The case studies and selected statements are based on real articles and associated comments.

Please note: The case studies include descriptions or language that could be considered offensive or triggering. They are intended for educational purposes only.

ARTICLE TITLE

„Annalena Baerbock steps back from green faction leadership role”

Context: Annalena Baerbock is a German Member of Parliament and has been the German minister of foreign affairs from December 2021 to May 2025. In 2025 she withdrew from the leadership of the green faction in the German parliament.

COMMENT

“This woman is as stupid as half a meter of a field path.”

COMMENT

“We live inclusion. But to have the mentally retarded as highest representatives of the people is too much of a good thing. A closed institution would have been better!”

COMMENT

“[She] should rather go clean somewhere instead of staying in politics. This woman is not worth a penny there.”

Context: The depicted woman is Tessa Ganserer, one of the first trans Members of Parliament in Germany. She posted this photo on her own channel.

A right-wing politician (Beatrix von Storch) reposted this image and subtitled it with a message that gender cannot be changed.

COMMENT

“Harbor Hooker.”

Greta Thunberg ✓

20. August · 🌐

I'm currently joining the biggest mobilisation ever against Norwegian oil, ahead of their defining election in September. Hundreds of activists from all over Europe just blocked the country's biggest oil terminal for 36 hours, and more actions await.

Norway being Europe's biggest oil producer has blood on its hands. Despite its attempts to make itself appear as a voice for peace and sustainability, its oil causes death and destruction over the globe.

Context: Greta Thunberg is a famous climate and social justice activist. She founded the *Fridays for Future* movement and has been very vocal about the israel-palestine-conflict. In this post she updated her followers about a project she conducted during a visit in Norway.

COMMENT

“Just plain stupid and attention-hungry... we don't drive combustion engines for fun... [...] and those Gaza actions are just stupid... [...] Thunberg has destroyed the reputation and purpose of Fridays for Future.”

Annalena Baerbock is not only a political figure, but a former minister of foreign affairs as well as a former leader of a parliamentary faction. Thus, she must endure a higher level of scrutiny than an ordinary individual.

The first comment primarily refers to the person Baerbock, and hardly to any specific behaviour. It is therefore not factually related to the original post. It employs a derogatory German figure of speech and presents an absolutised judgment of Baerbock as a person. This particular expression of opinion is of only minor relevance to public opinion formation, but it reaches a very large audience on the internet.

The second comment refers to Baerbock's ability to hold a political office. It employs highly polemical and discriminatory language. While there is a loose factual connection between the role Baerbock exercises politically and the content of the comment, the remark also concerns Baerbock as a person independently of her office, particularly because intelligence is closely linked to the mere existence of a human being.

At the same time, the comment polemicalises the treatment of people with disabilities, as endorsed by Green Party policies. Thus, the comment rather falls into a grey area. It also illustrates that merely (mis-)categorizing a person as a member of a marginalized group can constitute an insult, even though discrimination against such groups is itself prohibited.

The last comment discriminates against Baerbock in a misogynistic manner. Both sentences must be read together. While the second part addresses Baerbock's unsuitability for political office in comparatively neutral language, the first sentence reduces her to her gender. Pure misogyny (or any other form of discrimination) does not necessarily constitute an insult against an individual. The first sentence refers to a behaviour (holding office) and the abilities assumed relevant to it (being a man). Such discriminatory statements are protected by *freedom of expression*, even if they are narrow-minded and factually incorrect.

Two possible insults may be hidden behind this post: one is Beatrix von Storch's statement and the other is the comment. Whether intentional misgendering constitutes an insult is largely unsettled. In the context of Ganserer, however, it has been judicially ruled that, at least in the immediate temporal context of a debate on the *Self-Determination Act*, it does not constitute a criminal insult, but merely a very critical and polemical contribution to political opinion formation.

The second comment employs a simple swear word without further elaboration. This gives the impression that the author intended merely to offend rather than contribute substantively. Moreover, the fact that Ganserer posed suggestively for a photo does not justify this directness, particularly when the original post concerned the visibility of trans persons. A counterfactual test can help assess this: a more factual contribution would have critiqued the public presentation in this pose and attire. However, this test must not lead to the assumption that only polite and formal statements are permissible. Overall, exaggerated language is legal, regardless of the feelings of the person concerned.

Greta Thunberg is a public figure who has gained attention through her fight against climate change and her involvement in the Middle East conflict. In doing so, she occasionally uses language and actions that are perceived as radical. The comment points out several aspects with which the author disagrees. However, it primarily criticises Thunberg's political statements and her activism. It is unclear whether the introductory words "just plain stupid" refer to Thunberg herself or to the action she presented in Norway. In such cases, the interpretation most favourable to the author should be assumed.

Significance for public opinion-forming / public interest

The *Freedom of Speech* is a fundamental right that encompasses both the very human desire to individual expression as well as the prerequisite of a democratic society to argue about public affairs. The more a matter is a public one the more weight the freedom of speech holds. That does not necessarily only concern political statements.

Context of the expression

The context of the expression can vary and is probably a very relevant circumstance to factor into your decision. Here, it is used as an umbrella term for a plethora of different situations. The time and place of an expression may be considered, as well as the audience it reaches, whether it is satire or art (which are additionally constitutionally protected). It is also relevant whether there has been a dispute or a verbal altercation between the involved parties beforehand.

Content of the expression

The content of the expression likewise has a major influence on its legality. Especially when swear words are used an expression clearly constitutes an insult. Likewise, objectively expressed criticism is fully protected by freedom of expression. In between, it should be considered whether there is factual connection between occasion and expression.

Context of the person concerned

All people are protected by the general personality right. However, if the individual in question is a public figure, this protection is reduced. People in political life or those closely connected to the state must tolerate significant limitations so that a democratic process of opinion forming by free discourse can be ensured.

Impact on the person concerned

The consequences of statements can have substantial effects on the individual concerned. In evaluating them, particular consideration must be given to the impact on the person's social life and economic livelihood. The size of the audience to which the statement is addressed may also be relevant.

These supplementary materials are part of the KAPAZ material collection. They correspond to the guidelines “Fortify research institutions” and the practical toolkit “Practicing Support Strategies”

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